

The spatial-temporal ordering of amyloid pathology and opportunities for PET imaging

Enrico Fantoni¹, Lyduine Collij^{*2}, Isadora Lopes Alves², Christopher Buckley¹, Gill Farrar¹, *on behalf of the AMYPAD consortium*

1. GE Healthcare, Life Sciences – Pharmaceutical Diagnostics, Chalfont St. Giles, Buckinghamshire, United Kingdom
2. Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Department of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine, De Boelelaan 1117, Amsterdam, Netherlands

(* both authors contributed equally to this work)

Corresponding Author

Gill Farrar
GE Healthcare, Life Sciences
Gill.Farrar@ge.com

Noteworthy:

- The regional-temporal evolution of amyloid pathology may enable the earlier identification of subjects who are in the Alzheimer's Disease pathological continuum (pages 6,7 and *8)
- Cortical deposition generally precedes striatal pathology, and in PET-only studies, medial cortical regions are seen to accumulate amyloid earlier than lateral regions (pages 8 and 12)
- Models for staging amyloid pathology could improve subject selection into secondary prevention trials and visual assessment in clinical routine (pages 3, 14)

ABSTRACT

While clinical routine focuses on dichotomous and visual interpretation of amyloid PET, in research settings, regional image assessment may yield additional opportunities. Understanding the regional-temporal evolution of amyloid pathology may enable earlier identification of subjects in the Alzheimer's Disease pathological continuum, as well as a more fine-grained assessment of pathology beyond traditional dichotomous measures. This review summarizes current research in the detection of regional amyloid deposition patterns and its potential for staging amyloid pathology. Pathology studies, cross-sectional and longitudinal PET-only studies, and comparative PET and autopsy studies are included. Despite certain differences, cortical deposition generally precedes striatal pathology, and in PET-only studies, medial cortical regions are seen to accumulate amyloid earlier than lateral regions. Based on regional amyloid PET, multiple studies have developed and implemented models for staging amyloid pathology which could improve subject selection into secondary prevention trials and visual assessment in clinical routine.

KEY WORDS

Amyloid PET

Staging

Spatial-temporal ordering

Pathology

INTRODUCTION

Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging allows the visualization and quantification of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) plaques, a key physio-pathological hallmark for the placement of individuals along the Alzheimer's Disease (AD) continuum (1). Clinically, brain PET images are visually inspected and reported as a binary negative or positive read after assessment of several regions. Positive scans, indicative of moderate and frequent plaque density, are determined by the presence of elevated signal in at least one of four or five key read regions: frontal lobe, posterior cingulate and precuneus, parietal lobe, lateral temporal lobe, and (specifically for ^{18}F -Flutemetamol (^{18}F -FMM) scans) striatum (2,3). All research (^{11}C -Pittsburg Compound-B (^{11}C -PIB)(4) and commercially approved tracers (^{18}F -FMM)(5), ^{18}F -Florbetaben (^{18}F -FBB)(6), ^{18}F -Florbetapir (^{18}F -FBP)(7) display 85-98% sensitivity and 87-100% specificity for $A\beta$ plaques when using CERAD or NIA-AA post-mortem truth standards (8-12). Additionally, a focused ^{18}F -FMM PET striatal read accuracy has been demonstrated to detect striatal plaques with 69-87% sensitivity and 96-100% specificity (13).

Despite routine clinical focus on binary negative/positive image interpretation, there is increasing interest in assessment of individual brain regions in the sequential accumulation of amyloid (14). Whilst dichotomous patient-based PET reading provides the currently approved method to evaluate amyloid deposition (1,15), regional brain measures using quantitative methods may provide valuable information, especially during early phases of accumulation when individuals have few clinical symptoms (16-18). Conversely, later in the disease spectrum, regional variations remain more modest with globally amyloid-positive PET measures in amnesic mild cognitive impairment (aMCI) patients being comparable in topography and intensity to end-of-life AD and non-AD subjects (19).

Taken together, recent reports suggest that regional patterns can be used to identify earliest signs of amyloid pathology and may indicate potential of conversion to dementia in later stages of the pathological process. In this context, this article critically synthesizes key research

in the field of regional amyloid analysis, with the objective of advancing the overall understanding of amyloid PET's role in the evaluation of subjects in the earlier phases of the AD spectrum.

REVIEW OF METHODS USED ACROSS THE LITERATURE

Studies were grouped by methodology. The first focuses on histopathology at autopsy. Group two considers how PET can stage regional amyloid deposition relative to benchmark ordering method obtained by pathology. The third group assesses the frequency of regional PET amyloid uptake measures in cross-sectional cohorts, whilst the fourth concentrates on longitudinal studies. Studies are summarized in Table 1.

Group 1 - Post-Mortem Histology Studies

Histopathology is considered the gold standard method for amyloid plaque detection (19) with two landmark studies. Braak and Braak (20) evaluated the progressive topology and density of amyloid deposits in an analysis of 83 post-mortem brains from demented and non-demented elderly patients. Based on both frequency and density of plaques three stages of amyloid deposition were described, starting with deposits in basal portions of the frontal, temporal, and occipital lobes, followed by medium density deposits throughout cortical association areas, white matter and mild involvement of hippocampus, and ending with the inclusion of the sensorimotor cortex and expansion to subcortical structures, particularly striatum. Later, Thal et al. (14) followed a similar methodology, but statistically tested the presence of a constant sequence of regional amyloid deposition, adding strength to their proposed regional sequence compared to Braak albeit disregarding plaque density. In Thal et al., the first phase describes amyloid deposition in the whole neocortex with no mention of within-region differences, in contrast to the relatively more detailed regional assessment in Braak. In turn, 5 phases provide complementary information to Braak's description, focusing on the subsequent spreading of amyloid through subcortical regions.

Although post-mortem studies are considered the gold standard, limitations include the modest subject numbers and brain regions evaluated (14,20), and the focus on older end-of-life populations where other end-stage medical illnesses could further compromise the analysis (8).

Group 2 - Studies Comparing Amyloid PET Signal with Histology-based Regional Thal Staging

These studies utilized cohorts with both PET (visual and/or semi-quantitative evaluation) and autopsy data, which are highly informative but generally limited in availability.

Murray et al. (9) showed in a ¹¹C-PiB end-of-life cohort of 35 subjects, that incremental Thal phasing significantly predicts global SUVR signal increases, albeit in a modest population. A follow-up study (21) in 179 end-of-life subjects demonstrated that increases in a global PET measurement scale (Centiloid units (22)) are non-linearly related to Thal phases. Also, global ¹¹C-PiB PET only detected changes in Thal Phase 2, missing Phase 1 entirely. However, the authors suggested regional analysis could provide more sensitive estimates of early focal deposits compared to a global neocortical measure (9).

Similarly, in Thal 2015 (23), concordance between visual inspection of ¹⁸F-FMM and stages of amyloid phasing (Thal phases 0-5) were examined in a dual PET/autopsy 68-subject cohort. Visually negative amyloid PET was observed in cases with amyloid phases 1-2, whereas advanced pathology cases of phases 4-5 concurred with a positive scan. In the interim phase 3, only 33% of the cases were positive, indicating that this phase may represent an inflection point in the progression of amyloid that results in the ability to visually assign positivity to a scan.

Thal et al. additionally demonstrated in an extended cohort of 97 patients that ¹⁸F-FMM PET SUVR signal can be streamlined into 0-3 amyloid PET phase estimates. Using signal from either a combination of cortical regions and the caudate nucleus, this PET phasing strategy can act as surrogate for Thal phasing between phase 3 and 5 with 97% accuracy when allowing ± 1 Thal phase (24).

Group 3 - Ranking of Regional Amyloid Signal by PET-only Studies

Although limited by the lack of pathological confirmation, *in vivo* studies can implement a wide range of strategies to disentangle amyloid deposition patterns and have investigated the regional cortical involvement in more detail than previous post-mortem work. To date, most amyloid PET studies included subjects across the clinical AD spectrum (25-27), and only recent work has studied cognitively unimpaired (CU) subjects alone (28,29).

Huang et al. (25) ($N=36$) used a simple analysis of variance between volumes of interest to assess regional ^{18}F -FBP PET signal increments across clinical stages. They concluded that amyloid initially accumulates in precuneal, frontal, occipital and posterior cingulate areas. In a larger dataset ($N=222$), Villeneuve et al. (26) supported these findings by inferring a sequence of amyloid deposition from statistically significant signals of elevated ^{11}C -PiB Distribution Volume Ratio (DVR) between 66 permutations of 22-subject groups of interest with increasing mean ^{11}C -PiB DVR. With this analytical approach, the authors found an initial deposition of amyloid in medial cortical regions, followed by more lateral regions, finally involving the lateral temporal lobes. Finally, Cho et al. (27) also used cognitively healthy subjects as a reference group to obtain ^{18}F -FBB PET Z-transformed Standardized Uptake Value ratios (SUVR) from 195 subjects across the AD spectrum. The difference in frequency of regional involvement was assessed and then verified with bootstrapping statistics, allowing to determine rank confidence intervals and standard errors. In this work, the precuneus was reported to show early amyloid deposition, while the cingulate showed later involvement together with inferior temporal and the insula cortex, somewhat in contrast to previous studies (27).

More recently, studies have focused on amyloid PET signal from cognitively unimpaired (CU) subjects, aiming to capture amyloid accumulation, generally more apparent before cognitive impairment (30,31). One key study is Grothe et al. (28), which in addition to assessing a regional ordering of amyloid deposition was first to create a corresponding staging system based solely

on PET imaging. The authors ranked the frequency of regional involvement in amyloid deposition across 179 ADNI CU cases imaged with ^{18}F -FBP, essentially translating the traditional methodology from post-mortem studies to PET imaging. With this method, 4 stages of amyloid deposition were described, where early involvement of temporal regions was more pronounced than in previous work. (Figure 1).

Sakr et al. 2019 (32) further demonstrated that Grothe's 2017 model can be applied to a different cohort of 318 subjective cognitive impairment (SCI) subjects (33) scanned with ^{18}F -FBP PET, with only few subjects deviating from the model. However, when re-computing the model in this SCI cohort, important discrepancies such as a more frequent involvement of posterior and lateral temporal regions were noted. The authors suggested age differences between cohorts could explain altered regional deposition patterns due to e.g. late-age comorbidities (32).

Although results from Sakr (32) suggest between-tracer translatability of staging models, this could not be reproduced in Lopes Alves et al. (29). In this work, an event-based ordering of regional amyloid deposition was investigated in three cohorts ($N=1267$ subjects) across the full AD spectrum. Based on a probabilistic approach, a deterministic event-based model (dEBM) (34) learnt the temporal ordering of biomarker changes from normal to abnormal in large cross-sectional datasets. Regions were ranked based on their probability of abnormality and a population-wide ordering was determined by minimizing cross-subject differences. The three radiotracer datasets presented variations in regional probability of accumulation especially in temporal and frontal regions. In turn, the striatum appeared in later stages for all tracers.

Considering the above, recent work by Collij et al. focused on overcoming the potential lack of cross-cohort and cross-tracer validity of previous staging models (35). Here, a 5-stage model was constructed from PET imaging data from 989 cognitively unimpaired subjects originating from 6 cohorts and scanned with one of 4 different PET tracers. The methodology expanded on earlier work from Grothe et al., with additional tests for abnormality cut-offs and alternative stage definitions. The first stage of deposition started in cingulate regions, followed by

precuneus, inferior parietal, paracentral gyrus, lateral orbital and middle frontal, and insular cortex in Stage 2. Then, basal temporal, and associative parietal and frontal depositions were present in Stage 3, and finally other temporal and occipital regions involved in Stage 4 (Figure 1). These results suggest that by incorporating the intrinsic heterogeneity in population and available tracer, it is possible to construct a more generalizable staging system, applicable to increasingly common multi-tracer studies.

Studies in this section describe a range of strategies to understand the regional ordering of amyloid deposition and potentially transform this knowledge into staging systems. Despite differences, different studies were able to translate a temporal pattern of amyloid accumulation into a system for staging amyloid burden. Nonetheless, despite an overall agreement in a broad ordering of amyloid deposition, there is not a complete match in the final staging systems. This indicates that a universal staging system would either have to account for heterogeneity or allow a degree of variability to be accounted for, and further investigation is needed to determine whether the proposed staging models have distinct applications in a clinical setting or to support clinical trials.

Group 4 - Studies Based on Longitudinal PET Imaging

These final studies used longitudinal PET data to derive the sequential ordering of amyloid deposition. These are suited to describing the dynamic amyloid spatial-temporal deposition pattern and can effectively account for population differences in A β burden, age-related non-specific A β accumulation rates, and disease stage heterogeneities.

Hanseeuw et al. (36) based their methods on *a priori* knowledge from post-mortem studies that striatal amyloid deposition is generally preceded by cortical involvement. They hypothesized a higher likelihood of transition of amyloid deposition from cortical to striatal regions than vice versa (14). Longitudinal PET data obtained from ¹⁸F-FBP and ¹¹C-PiB scans from 1433 patients along the full dementia spectrum were used to assess the hypothesis and define three PET stages

of amyloidosis: 1) low overall PET signal, 2) high PET signal in cortex only, and 3) high PET signal in both cortex and striatum. With the available serial PET measures, individual trajectories advanced successfully through these three stages, providing longitudinal support to previous reports showing the striatum is affected by amyloid deposition only *after* cortical involvement.

More recently, Palmqvist et al. (37) also assessed the longitudinal patterns in amyloid deposition from PET images, but grounded their analyses on an independent amyloid biomarker, namely CSF A β_{42} . The authors hypothesized that early regions of amyloid deposition are those which display increasing accumulation rates (in SUVR/year) when comparing CSF-/PET- to CSF+/PET- subjects (38). Conversely, regions where accumulation rates are higher in CSF+/PET+ compared with CSF+/PET- individuals would be those that are affected at a later stage in the disease process. Their results described the cingulate, orbitofrontal, precuneus and insula as early regions. Central, occipital, temporal and some limited frontal regions were identified as later regions. Results were then successfully replicated in a separate population from the BioFINDER cohort (39).

Recently, Palmqvist's work has been expanded by Mattsson and colleagues to construct a longitudinally valid staging model again grounded on CSF A β_{42} . In addition to the identification of the early and late regions as per Palmqvist's methodology, this work defined an intermediate period by identifying remaining regions with longitudinal accumulation that did not distinguish early or late processes (40). From this replication and extended work, Mattsson and colleagues were limited to identifying 3 stages of amyloid accumulation. The first stage was defined by the precuneus, posterior and isthmus cingulate, insula, and medial and lateral orbitofrontal cortices. The second stage involved medial and lateral frontal, lateral parietal, temporal and additional occipital regions, and the final stage described amyloid accumulation in the lingual, pericalcarine, paracentral, precentral and postcentral cortices (Figure 1). This model was then applied to two cohorts and successfully staged 2039 PET scans from 741 participants.

DISCUSSION OF APPLIED METHODOLOGIES

There are important methodologic discrepancies between studies (Table 1) such as the presence/absence of histological post-mortem validation, sample size and cohort composition, as well as whether longitudinal data was present or a temporal ordering was inferred from cross-sectional observations. Some of these methodological differences may be responsible for the discrepant regional sequences observed. For instance, entorhinal cortical accumulation occurs early in an autopsy study (14), but several PET studies contradict this (27,35). Cingulate and medial frontal regions accumulate early in most PET studies (26-29,35,37), however other early regions such as precuneus are less robustly reported.

In addition, some more subtle differences inherent to PET imaging may play a role. Firstly, the choice of biomarker may lead to variations in the detection of amyloid plaques (26,28). Stilbene-derived amyloid PET radiotracers may be less sensitive for detection of diffuse amyloid compared to thioflavin-derived tracers although head to head analysis of tracer uptake would be helpful to confirm this hypothesis (36,37,41). Additionally, a decreased PET sensitivity to amyloid at the extremes of deposition could occur; the first regional deposits with low amyloid concentrations may be missed by global PET imaging (9,12,23) and end-of-life regional deposits are often masked by cerebral atrophy (2,42). PET amyloid tracers also have varying dynamic ranges in terms of the maximum signal strength in positive compared to negative cases (35). This could lead to discrepancies when comparing scans from different tracers, hence the value of normalization measures such as the Centiloid scale (22). Alternatively, when a tracer harmonization strategy is not implemented, staging models can be made more robust by integrating data from multiple tracers (35).

Furthermore, regional PET signal quantification is subject to methodological differences across studies even when using the same radiotracer (

Table 1). This includes the inconsistent use of reference regions (26), partial volume correction (23,26,32), the increased risk of segmentation and co-registration errors compared to global quantification (43), as well as a variable choice of regional and global SUVr cut-offs (26-28,32). Furthermore, the regional detail of staging schemes can vary substantially, considering that very detailed staging schemes run the risk of high unstageability rates. Therefore, a compromise ensuring an abundance of brain regions are considered is usually necessary (28,32). This is compounded by the inter-study variability of use of PET anatomical atlases and histological brain sections (44).

Lastly, different factors can act as confounders and only some of the studies include a verification step to ensure variables do not detract from the robustness of the observations. The presence of a genetic predisposition to AD (such as the APOE ϵ 4 allele) (36,37,45), an imbalanced age distribution (9), cognitive brain reserve (46), brain weight (9), cortical thickness (37) or the presence of wide-spread diffuse plaques instead of neuritic plaques (41) and comorbidities such as cerebral amyloid angiopathy (9,32,47) can all affect amyloid plaque distribution and the analysis of the PET signal.

The variety of methods employed by these studies ultimately provides a broader picture of amyloid accumulation patterns. Generally consistent results across all studies point to the possibility of identifying a high-level ordering of cerebral amyloid deposition, while details in regional ordering can be substantially affected by population and tracer differences (28,32) and generalizable staging models may need to allow a degree of heterogeneity to achieve high applicability. Therefore, the use of multiple cohorts, distinct model generation and validation cohorts, biomarkers and staging methods (35,40) is arguably the most appropriate strategy to derive both a sequence of regional deposition and a staging model with universal validity.

SYNTHESIS OF RESULTS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR REGIONAL AMYLOID PET

The diversity of approaches reveal that a universally applicable regional amyloid staging strategy requires consideration of the above discussed methodological discrepancies. Nonetheless, some preliminary all-encompassing agreements about the process of amyloid accumulation can be derived.

Cortical Generally Precedes Striatal Accumulation

This is apparent from histological (14,20) and PET studies where subcortical regions are included (24,28,29,32,35,36). Thal et al. (14) justify this order by postulating a sequential amyloid accumulation along neutrally connected areas, with the striatal region receiving inputs from the neocortex (48). Palmqvist (37) and Cho (27) carry this argument one step further, by suggesting a Default Mode Network-driven mechanism for the regional accumulation process. In fact, a number of studies discussed in this review showed that striatal amyloid correlates to worsening cognitive scores and may be indicative of the potential transition from preclinical to clinical AD (14,28,36). However, the region is characterized by a predominance of amyloid plaques of diffuse form, which amyloid tracers are less sensitive to compared to higher density neuritic plaques (41,49). Yet, the specificity of the thioflavin tracers for detecting varying densities of amyloid plaques in this region is high (13,50,51) and hence the striatum therefore may have a unique potential to stage patients and assess the risk of disease progression.

In PET Studies, Medial Neocortical Regions are Seen to Accumulate Amyloid Earlier than Lateral Regions

In subjects with moderate amyloid load, medial cortical regions are often more visually intense than lateral regions in amyloid PET scans (8,52,53), despite autopsy evaluation indicating that lateral aspects of temporal, frontal and parietal lobes are involved earlier in the disease than medial regions (14,20,47). In order to examine this trend, Smith and Buckley (54) performed a post-hoc analysis on a substantial sub-cohort of subjects from the ¹⁸F-FMM autopsy validation

cohort ($N=106$) (12) and examined medial and lateral regions with similar levels of pathology. They showed that medial regions were read positive in over 20% more cases than lateral regions despite comparable pathology measures.

One possible explanation for these differences is PET signal distortion, derived from partial volume overlap effect between regions. The proximity of medial regions to white matter and additional grey matter signal from contralateral hemisphere could raise a region's relative intensity, adding to true tracer signal. Conversely, in lateral regions, the lack of intensity in juxtaposed regions results in decreased signal due to spill-out into interstitial cranial regions.

As a side-effect of this signal distortion, medial regions (easily accessible from a para-sagittal plane) can be helpful to visually detect (early) amyloid deposits with high sensitivity. However, when discussing the true regional amyloid deposition sequence, it is important to consider that the PET signal might represent a heterogeneous distortion of an otherwise uniform tracer distribution. Thus, uncorrected regional averages of quantitative data could bear influence on composite scores and possible order of staging when examining early amyloid deposition.

The Placement of Temporal Regions in the Pathological Ordering is Remarkably Variable across Studies

Early deposition in temporal regions is particularly observed in studies employing ^{18}F -FBP PET (25,28,32), while elsewhere is described as a rather late accumulating region (26,35,37), perhaps paralleling the distinct processes of cognitive degeneration and ageing as has been suggested by Chetelat et al. (55,56). From the studies employing ^{18}F -FBP PET covered here (**Error! Reference source not found.**), only Palmqvist and Mattson do not report temporal regions as one of the earliest to display amyloid accumulation. Compared to other ^{18}F -FBP studies, the main difference in these studies can be attributed to the use of longitudinal PET imaging to derive the ordering of regional accumulation. In view of Chetelat's findings of a distinct pattern between individuals aged 20-50 years old and elderly subjects, it is possible that temporal regions have increased signal in mid-life and therefore display an elevated PET signal at baseline.

This pattern would then be captured when assessing cross-sectional studies of elderly subjects with overall low amyloid PET uptake but would be missed when accounting for longitudinal rates of accumulation starting at 50 years of age or older. However, the reason for this observation being restricted to ¹⁸F-FBP scans remains unknown.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The quest to determine the most likely temporal order of regional amyloid deposition in AD benefits from studies examining the diverse range of cohorts of ever-increasing size and heterogeneity. The understanding of this progressive accumulation process has considerably evolved since the first regional autopsy analysis in 1991 (20), and methods are becoming more sophisticated, now integrating cohorts utilizing different amyloid biomarkers as well as utilizing diverse techniques to model and validate the order of deposition (Figure 1).

Broadly speaking, multiple studies indicate that neocortex precedes striatal deposition, and that cortical accumulation appears earliest in medial frontal and cingulate regions, then spreading throughout the neocortex and being generally found late in occipital regions. As the pathology progresses, amyloid deposits spread to striatum, hippocampus and entorhinal regions, then extend further within subcortical regions and into cerebellum. The exact cortical ordering however remains diversely described, which perhaps reflects different spatial-temporal deposition patterns inherent to different subpopulations, amyloid detection techniques and settings (Figure 1).

Despite residual variability across studies, multiple attempts to create and apply staging systems to assess the extent of amyloid burden with PET imaging have been successful. These efforts indicate there is utility in a relatively broad knowledge of the spatial-temporal development of amyloid plaques. Currently approved amyloid PET imaging methods relate to an overall visual inspection of brain scans as either positive or negative. However, considering the body of work described here, future image assessment could progress to having an element of regional

evaluation using (semi-)quantitative PET imaging methods. This could take specific advantage of the high plaque detection sensitivity offered by medial brain regions, as well as of the high specificity towards varying densities of deposited plaques offered by striatal image read. Regional image reads could be used to assist with identification of subjects for earlier therapeutic intervention and patient staging with a more tailored management approach.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

GF and CB are or were (EF) full time employees of GE Healthcare.

LC and ILA are affiliated with the Amsterdam University Medical Center, location VUmc.

No other potential conflicts of interest relevant to this article exist.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The project leading to this paper has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 115952. This Joint Undertaking receives the support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

REFERENCES

1. Jack CR, Jr., Bennett DA, Blennow K, et al. NIA-AA Research Framework: Toward a biological definition of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2018;14:535-562.
2. Buckley CJ, Sherwin PF, Smith AP, Wolber J, Weick SM, Brooks DJ. Validation of an electronic image reader training programme for interpretation of [18F]flutemetamol beta-amyloid PET brain images. *Nucl Med Commun*. 2017;38:234-241.
3. Healthcare G. Vizamyl (Flutemetamol F 18 Injection) electronic reader training programme. <https://www.readvizamyl.com/>. Accessed 2018-03-02.
4. Klunk WE, Engler H, Nordberg A, et al. Imaging brain amyloid in Alzheimer's disease with Pittsburgh Compound-B. *Ann Neurol*. 2004;55:306-319.
5. FDA. US Prescribing information for Vizamyl. http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2017/203137s008lbl.pdf. Accessed 2017-03-16.
6. FDA. US Prescribing information for Neuraceq. http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2016/204677s012lbl.pdf. Accessed 2017-03-20.
7. FDA. US Prescribing information for Amyvid. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2013/202008s020lbl.pdf. Accessed 2017-03-20.
8. Sabri O, Sabbagh MN, Seibyl J, et al. Florbetaben PET imaging to detect amyloid beta plaques in Alzheimer's disease: phase 3 study. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2015;11:964-974.
9. Murray ME, Lowe VJ, Graff-Radford NR, et al. Clinicopathologic and 11C-Pittsburgh compound B implications of Thal amyloid phase across the Alzheimer's disease spectrum. *Brain*. 2015;138:1370-1381.
10. Clark CM, Pontecorvo MJ, Beach TG, et al. Cerebral PET with florbetapir compared with neuropathology at autopsy for detection of neuritic amyloid-beta plaques: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Neurol*. 2012;11:669-678.
11. Curtis C, Gamez JE, Singh U, et al. Phase 3 trial of flutemetamol labeled with radioactive fluorine 18 imaging and neuritic plaque density. *JAMA Neurol*. 2015;72:287-294.
12. Salloway S, Gamez JE, Singh U, et al. Performance of [(18)F]flutemetamol amyloid imaging against the neuritic plaque component of CERAD and the current (2012) NIA-AA recommendations for the neuropathologic diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement (Amst)*. 2017;9:25-34.
13. Beach TG, Thal DR, Zhanette M, Smith A, Buckley C. Detection of Striatal Amyloid Plaques with [18F]flutemetamol: Validation with Postmortem Histopathology. *J Alzheimers Dis*. 2016;52:863-873.
14. Thal DR, Rub U, Orantes M, Braak H. Phases of A beta-deposition in the human brain and its relevance for the development of AD. *Neurology*. 2002;58:1791-1800.
15. Dubois B, Hampel H, Feldman HH, et al. Preclinical Alzheimer's disease: Definition, natural history, and diagnostic criteria. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2016;12:292-323.

16. Cohen AD, Mowrey W, Weissfeld LA, et al. Classification of amyloid-positivity in controls: comparison of visual read and quantitative approaches. *Neuroimage*. 2013;71:207-215.
17. Chetelat G, Murray ME. Amyloid PET scan: Staging beyond reading? *Neurology*. 2017;89:2029-2030.
18. Collij LE, Konijnenberg E, Reimand J, et al. Assessing amyloid pathology in cognitively normal subjects using 18F-flutemetamol PET: comparing visual reads and quantitative methods. *J Nucl Med*. 2019;60:541-547.
19. McKhann GM, Knopman DS, Chertkow H, et al. The diagnosis of dementia due to Alzheimer's disease: recommendations from the National Institute on Aging-Alzheimer's Association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2011;7:263-269.
20. Braak H, Braak E. Neuropathological staging of Alzheimer-related changes. *Acta Neuropathol*. 1991;82:239-259.
21. La Joie R, Ayakta N, Seeley WW, et al. Multisite study of the relationships between antemortem [(11)C]PIB-PET Centiloid values and postmortem measures of Alzheimer's disease neuropathology. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2019;15:205-216.
22. Klunk WE, Koeppe RA, Price JC, et al. The Centiloid Project: standardizing quantitative amyloid plaque estimation by PET. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2015;11:1-15 e11-14.
23. Thal DR, Beach TG, Zanette M, et al. [(18)F]flutemetamol amyloid positron emission tomography in preclinical and symptomatic Alzheimer's disease: specific detection of advanced phases of amyloid-beta pathology. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2015;11:975-985.
24. Thal DR, Beach TG, Zanette M, et al. Estimation of amyloid distribution by [(18)F]flutemetamol PET predicts the neuropathological phase of amyloid beta-protein deposition. *Acta Neuropathol*. 2018;136:557-567.
25. Huang KL, Lin KJ, Hsiao IT, et al. Regional amyloid deposition in amnesic mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease evaluated by [18F]AV-45 positron emission tomography in Chinese population. *PLoS One*. 2013;8:e58974.
26. Villeneuve S, Rabinovici GD, Cohn-Sheehy BI, et al. Existing Pittsburgh Compound-B positron emission tomography thresholds are too high: statistical and pathological evaluation. *Brain*. 2015;138:2020-2033.
27. Cho H, Choi JY, Hwang MS, et al. In vivo cortical spreading pattern of tau and amyloid in the Alzheimer disease spectrum. *Ann Neurol*. 2016;80:247-258.
28. Grothe MJ, Barthel H, Sepulcre J, et al. In vivo staging of regional amyloid deposition. *Neurology*. 2017;89:2031-2038.
29. Lopes-Alves I, Collij L, Heeman F, et al. EVENT-BASED MODELING OF THE TEMPORAL ORDERING OF REGIONAL β -AMYLOID DEPOSITION IN THE BRAIN. *Alzheimer's & Dementia: The Journal of the Alzheimer's Association*. 2018;14:P887-P888.

30. Jack CR, Jr., Wiste HJ, Lesnick TG, et al. Brain beta-amyloid load approaches a plateau. *Neurology*. 2013;80:890-896.
31. Donohue MC, Sperling RA, Petersen R, et al. Association Between Elevated Brain Amyloid and Subsequent Cognitive Decline Among Cognitively Normal Persons. *JAMA*. 2017;317:2305-2316.
32. Sakr FA, Grothe MJ, Cavedo E, et al. Applicability of in vivo staging of regional amyloid burden in a cognitively normal cohort with subjective memory complaints: the INSIGHT-preAD study. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2019;11:15.
33. Jessen F, Amariglio RE, van Boxtel M, et al. A conceptual framework for research on subjective cognitive decline in preclinical Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2014;10:844-852.
34. Venkatraghavan A, Bron EE, Niessen WJ, S. K. A discriminative event based model for Alzheimer's Disease Progression Modelling. In: (eds) NMea, ed. *Information Processing in Medical Imaging. IPMI 2017. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Vol 10265.: Springer, Cham; 2017.
35. Collij LE HF, Salvadó G, Altomare D, Wilde de A, Konijnenberg E, Buchem van M, Yaqub M, Markiewicz P, Golla S, Wottschel V, Wink AM, Visser PJ, Lammertsma AA, Scheltens P, Flier van der W, Boellaard R, Berckel van BNM, Gispert JD, Schmidt M, Barkhof F, Lopes Alves I, On behalf of the AMYPAD consortium. P137: Staging cortical amyloid deposition using PET imaging. *Human Amyloid Imaging Conference*. 2019;379-380.
36. Hanseeuw BJ, Betensky RA, Mormino EC, et al. PET staging of amyloidosis using striatum. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2018;14:1281-1292.
37. Palmqvist S, Scholl M, Strandberg O, et al. Earliest accumulation of beta-amyloid occurs within the default-mode network and concurrently affects brain connectivity. *Nat Commun*. 2017;8:1214.
38. Mattsson N, Insel PS, Donohue M, et al. Independent information from cerebrospinal fluid amyloid-beta and florbetapir imaging in Alzheimer's disease. *Brain*. 2015;138:772-783.
39. Hansson O, Seibyl J, Stomrud E, et al. CSF biomarkers of Alzheimer's disease concord with amyloid-beta PET and predict clinical progression: A study of fully automated immunoassays in BioFINDER and ADNI cohorts. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2018;14:1470-1481.
40. Mattsson N, Palmqvist S, Stomrud E, Vogel J, Hansson O. Staging beta-Amyloid Pathology With Amyloid Positron Emission Tomography. *JAMA Neurol*. 2019.
41. Ikonomic MD, Fantoni ER, Farrar G, Salloway S. Infrequent false positive [(18)F]flutemetamol PET signal is resolved by combined histological assessment of neuritic and diffuse plaques. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2018;10:60.
42. Seibyl J, Catafau AM, Barthel H, et al. Impact of Training Method on the Robustness of the Visual Assessment of 18F-Florbetaben PET Scans: Results from a Phase-3 Study. *J Nucl Med*. 2016;57:900-906.
43. Landau SM, Fero A, Baker SL, et al. Measurement of longitudinal beta-amyloid change with 18F-florbetapir PET and standardized uptake value ratios. *J Nucl Med*. 2015;56:567-574.

44. Schmidt ME, Chiao P, Klein G, et al. The influence of biological and technical factors on quantitative analysis of amyloid PET: Points to consider and recommendations for controlling variability in longitudinal data. *Alzheimers Dement.* 2015;11:1050-1068.
45. Hanseeuw BJ, Jonas V, Jackson J, et al. Association of anxiety with subcortical amyloidosis in cognitively normal older adults. *Mol Psychiatry.* 2018.
46. Bauckneht M, Picco A, Nobili F, Morbelli S. Amyloid positron emission tomography and cognitive reserve. *World J Radiol.* 2015;7:475-483.
47. Ikonomic MD, Buckley CJ, Heurling K, et al. Post-mortem histopathology underlying beta-amyloid PET imaging following flutemetamol F 18 injection. *Acta Neuropathol Commun.* 2016;4:130.
48. Braak H, Braak E, Yilmazer D, de Vos RA, Jansen EN, Bohl J. Pattern of brain destruction in Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases. *J Neural Transm (Vienna).* 1996;103:455-490.
49. Ikonomic MD, Klunk WE, Abrahamson EE, et al. Post-mortem correlates of in vivo PiB-PET amyloid imaging in a typical case of Alzheimer's disease. *Brain.* 2008;131:1630-1645.
50. Klunk WE, Price JC, Mathis CA, et al. Amyloid deposition begins in the striatum of presenilin-1 mutation carriers from two unrelated pedigrees. *J Neurosci.* 2007;27:6174-6184.
51. Villemagne VL, Ataka S, Mizuno T, et al. High striatal amyloid beta-peptide deposition across different autosomal Alzheimer disease mutation types. *Arch Neurol.* 2009;66:1537-1544.
52. Vandenberghe R, Van Laere K, Ivanoiu A, et al. 18F-flutemetamol amyloid imaging in Alzheimer disease and mild cognitive impairment: a phase 2 trial. *Ann Neurol.* 2010;68:319-329.
53. Pontecorvo MJ, Arora AK, Devine M, et al. Quantitation of PET signal as an adjunct to visual interpretation of florbetapir imaging. *Eur J Nucl Med Mol Imaging.* 2017;44:825-837.
54. Smith A, Buckley C. [18F]flutemetamol PET image representation of Ab pathology; differences between lateral and medial image intensity for equivalent levels of pathology. *10th Human Amyloid Imaging.* Miami, FL, USA; 2016.
55. Villain N, Chételat G, Grassiot B, et al. Regional dynamics of amyloid-beta deposition in healthy elderly, mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease: a voxelwise PiB-PET longitudinal study. *Brain.* 2012;135:2126-2139.
56. Chételat G, Villemagne VL, Villain N, et al. Accelerated cortical atrophy in cognitively normal elderly with high β -amyloid deposition. 2012;78:477-484.

Table 1 Studies evaluating regional amyloid deposition.

X = cross-sectional, L = longitudinal, FDS= full dementia spectrum, ES = early symptomatic, AS = asymptomatic, CN = cognitively normal, CSF = Cerebrospinal fluid; DVR = Distribution volume ratio, SUVR = Standardized Uptake value ratio; PVEC = partial volume effect correction (Y = yes; N = no); WM = White matter; “-“ = not applicable; n/k not known. The population is ethnically Caucasian unless otherwise specified.

Author, year	Methodology	Study Design	N [N model]	N Cohorts	Staged population (population used for staging model)	Percentage of clinical stages in the staged population CN/MCI/AD DEM/NON-AD DEM [model population]	Age mean (min-max) [model population]	N brain regions	Brain regions	Amyloid phases (N)	Amyloid biomarker	Regional cut-off determination	PVEC	Reference region	Deviations from staging (% cases)
Braak 1991 (20)	Descriptive observational	X	83	1	End of life FDS	65 / 10 / 25 / -	Old age (exact age: -)	24	Global	0-3 (4)	histology	Histological continuum	-	-	-
Thal 2002 (14)	Frequency analysis	X	47	1	End of life FDS	19 / 2 / 34 / 4 / 43 (n/k)	77.7 ± 10.9 (42-93)	-	Global	0-5 (6)	histology	Histological continuum	-	-	-
Huang 2013 (25)	Clinico-pathological analysis	X	36	1	FDS Chinese	31 / 36 (aMCI) / 33 / -	CN 69.3±6.6, aMCI 70.0±11.2, AD 75.8±5.7	7	Cortical	-	FBP	Global SUVR cut-off	N	Cerebellum (whole)	-
Villeneuve 2015 (26)	Cluster analysis	X	222	1	FDS	78 / 3 / 5 / 13	70.4	-	Cortical	-	PIB	Cut-offs from probability of subject belonging to a specific cluster	N	Cerebellar cortex	-
	Iterative voxel-based analysis											DVR continuum			
Cho 2016 (27)	Frequency analysis	X	195	1	FDS	34 / 12 (naMCI), 27 (aMCI) / 27 / -	CN 66.1±8.6, naMCI 68.5±7.8, aMCI 70.3±9.7, AD 74.9±8.1	25	Cortical	-	FBB	Global SUVR cut-off	Both N and Y	Cerebellar cortex	-
Grothe 2017 (28)	Frequency analysis	X	667 [179]	1	FDS [CN]	27 / 60 / 13 / - [100 / - / - / - / -]	CN 73.8±6.5, MCI 71.7±7.7, AD 75.6 ± 8.3	52	Global	0-4 (5)	FBP + CSF	Global SUVR cut-off	Y	Cerebellum	2%
Sakr 2019 (32)	Frequency analysis	X	318	1	ES/AS	100 / - / - / -	76.1 ± 3.5 (70-85)	52	Global	0-3 (4)	FBP	Global SUVR cut-off	Y	Cerebellum (whole)	1.30%

Lopes-Alves 2018 (29)	Event-based modelling	X	1267	3	FDS	57 / 4 / 25 / 14 (FMM) 84 / 6 / 9 / 1 (PIB) 84 / 7 / 8 / 1 (FBP)	CN 66.4 ± 9.0, MCI 69.5 ± 7.9, AD 68.4 ± 8.9, non AD 62.6 ± 6.0	21	Cortex + striatum	-	FMM, PIB, FBP	Regional specific implicit cut-offs from Gaussian Mixture Modelling	N	Cerebellar cortex	-
Collij 2019 (35)	Frequency analysis	X and L	3025 [989]	6	FDS [CN]	58 / 22 / 15 / 4 / 1 (n/k) [100 / - / - / -]	68.36 ± 8.75 [-]	27	Cortical	0-4 (5)	FBP, FMM, FBB, PIB	Global SUVR cut-off	Both N and Y	Cerebellar cortex	<1%
Palmqvist 2017 (37)	Longitudinal voxel- and ROI-wise accumulation rate comparison	L	406 [473]	2	ES/AS	34 / 66 / - / - [37 / 63 / - / -]	- [72.0±7.0]	68	Cortical	-	FBP, FMM + CSF	Global SUVR cut-off	Y	Composite	-
Mattsson 2019 (40)	Longitudinal ROI-based accumulation rate comparison	L	1215 [641]	2	FDS	41 / 52 / 7 [39 / 54 / 7]	-	68	Cortical + striatum	0-3 (4)	PIB, FBP + CSF	Global and model ROI SUVR cut-off	-	Composit	<2%
Hansseuw 2018 (36)	Longitudinal, Likelihood of transition	L	1433	2	FDS	45 / 40 / 15 / -	- (55-94)	2	Cortex vs striatum	0-2 (3)	PIB, FBP	By region	Y	PIB: cerebellar cortex FBP: Composite (cerebellum + WM)	0.25%
Murray 2015 (9)	Correlation of PET with Thal phasing (14)	X	35	1	End of life FDS	17 / 17 / 31 / 23	- (56-95)	1	Cortical	-	PIB + histology	Global SUVR cut-off	Y	Cerebellum (whole)	-
La Joie 2019 (21)	Correlation of PET with Thal phasing (14)	X	179	5	End of life FDS	12 / 15 / 35 / 37	73.0 ± 11.7	1	Cortical	-	PIB + histology	Gloal SUVR cut-off	N	Cerebellar crus gray median	-

Thal 2015 (23)	Correlation of PET with Thal phasing (Thal et., 2002)	X	68	1	End of life FDS	31 / - / 45 / 25	80.8 ± 8.19 (60-95)	5	Cortical	-	FMM + histology	Majority read from visual assessment	N	Cerebellar cortex and pons to exclude bias	-
Thal 2018 (24)	Regional threshold transition	X	97	2	End of life FDS	14 (non demented) / 67 / 19	72.8 ± 10.49 (non demented), 82.6 ± 7.69 AD, 80.7 ± 6.7 nonAD	6	Global	0-3 (4)	FMM + histology	Cortical composite and caudate nucleus SUVR cut-off	N	Pons	3.09% when allowing ±1 phase, otherwise 27.84%

Figure 1. General mapping of amyloid deposition order. VOI = volume of interest; SPM = statistical parametric mapping.

Study	Braak 1991	Thal 2002	Huang 2013	Villeneuve 2015	Cho 2016	Palmqvist 2017	Hanseeuw 2018	Mattsson 2019	Grothe 2017	Collij 2019						
Biomarker	Post-mortem histological data		In vivo biomarker analysis (PET and CSF)													
Clinical stages of model population	Full Dementia Spectrum (FDS)								Cognitively Unimpaired							
Brain regions considered	Global	Global	Cortical	Cortical	Cortical	Cortical	Cortex+Striatum	Cortical	Global	Cortical						
Staging system presented?	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes						
	Stage 0: No amyloid	Stage 0: No amyloid	No amyloid	No amyloid	No amyloid	No amyloid	Stage 0: No amyloid	Stage 0: No amyloid	Stage 0: No amyloid	Stage 0: No amyloid						
	Stage 1: Basal portions of the frontal, temporal and occipital lobe	Stage 1: Neocortex	Early: (aMCI compared to HC): posterior cingulate (only in VOI), precuneus frontal, temporal, parietal, occipital areas (VOI and SPM)	Early: Anterior cingulate, precuneus, medial frontal regions	Begins with: Middle and inferior temporal, middle frontal, orbitofrontal, inferior and superior frontal	Early: Medial orbitofrontal cortex, anterior cingulate cortex, insula, posterior and isthmus cingulate cortex, precuneus and to a lesser extent temporal regions	Stage 1: Neocortex	Stage 1: Precuneus, posterior and isthmus cingulate, insula and orbitofrontal cortices	Stage 1: Temporobasal, frontomedial, anterior cingulate	Stage 1: Cingulate regions						
Stage 2: Almost all neocortical association areas except for sensorimotor		Stage 2: Cingulate, insula, amygdala, entorhinal, hippocampus									Intermediate: Lateral frontal and parietal regions	Spreads in Following order: precuneus, anterior cingulate, supramarginal, superior temporal, posterior cingulate, parietal lobe, fusiform, insula, paracentral, lateral occipital, pre- and postcentral, lingual and medial occipital regions	Late: Lateral occipital, temporal, precentral, postcentral, paracentral and pericalcarine	Stage 2: Medial and lateral frontal, lateral parietal, temporal and occipital regions not pertaining to Stage 1 or 3	Stage 2: Temporal, frontal, precuneus and other parietal associative cortices	Stage 2: Precuneus, paracentral, orbitofrontal, inferior parietal, middle frontal, and insula
	Stage 3: Striatum, thalamus, hypothalamus, white matter	Late: (AD compared to aMCI): frontal, temporal and parietal regions (only in SPM)						Late: Entorhinal, hippocampus and amygdala	Stage 3: Primary sensory motor cortices and anterior medial temporal lobe	Stage 3: Basolateral temporal, and frontal and parietal associative cortices						
	Stage 4: Brainstem nuclei, pons and cerebellum															
Stage 3: Sensorimotor regions, subcortical structures and cerebellum	Stage 5: Cerebellum, basal ganglia, remaining brainstem															